

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING, HPTLC PROFILING AND ANTIBACTERIAL EFFECT OF VILVADI TABLET AGAINST *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS* AND METHICILLIN RESISTANT *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS* – AN IN VITRO STUDY

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 04/10/2022

Available online

31/10/2022

Keywords

Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, Vilvadi Tablet, *Staphylococcus aureus*, Antibacterial Activity, Antibiotic Resistance, MRSA.

ABSTRACT

Background: Antibiotic resistance is a global pandemic of the 21st century estimated to cause 10 million deaths a year by 2050. Bacterial multidrug resistance poses an ever increasing threat to mankind and we are at the dawn of post-antibiotic era. Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) comes under the high priority in the global priority pathogen list by WHO, is a well-recognized public health problem. Alternative medical practices including Ayurveda provides several age old wisdom in conditions of infections and epidemics. An in vitro study was conducted against *Staphylococcus aureus* (SA) and MRSA to test the efficacy of a common multi-herbal formulation, Vilvadi tablet (VT) which is indicated in Ayurveda for infections. Methodology: Successive solvent extraction with Cyclohexane (CH), Ethyl acetate (EA), Acetone (AC), and Methanol (MET) (70%) along with phytochemical screening and HPTLC profiling was done. The antibacterial activity was assessed using the Well diffusion method against Vancomycin as standard drug. The drug extracts were tested at doses of 15 µg/ml, 30 µg/ml, 60 µg/ml, 120 µg/ml, 240 µg/ml and 480 µg/ml. Minimal inhibitory concentration (MIC) was also determined for the extracts. Statistical analysis was performed using ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparison test against the standard Vancomycin. Statistical significance was fixed at 5 % level. Results and discussion: Phytochemical screening showed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, carbohydrates, tannins, phytosterols, glycosides, resins, fixed oils and fats. HPTLC profile showed 12 peaks and 9 peaks at 254nm and 366 nm respectively. In SA, AC (21.50±1.22 mm) and EA (21.33±1.55 mm) extracts at 480 µg/ml showed statistically significant inhibition as comparable to Vancomycin (24.67±1.15 mm). In MRSA, EA extract at 480 µg/ml (39.33±3.05 mm), 240 µg/ml (36.33±1.15 mm) and 120 µg/ml (28.67±1.15) and AC extract at 480 µg/ml (33.0±1.33), 240 µg/ml (28.00±2.00 mm) showed inhibition similar to that of standard drug (22.67±1.15 mm). The MIC for SA in EA extract was 143.9 µg/ml and for AC extract was 138.1 µg/ml respectively. In MRSA, EA extract showed a MIC of 123.91 µg/ml and AC extract showed 139.27 µg/ml respectively. Vancomycin on the other hand was reported to have an MIC of 0.25- 1 µg/ml for SA and 0.125-1 µg/ml for MRSA. Conclusion: The present study showed statistically significant inhibition of SA and MRSA by the AC and EA extracts of VT. A higher dose of 123.91 µg/ml and 139.27 µg/ml of EA and AC extracts were found equivalent to that of Vancomycin. These extracts at 480 µg/ml, 240 µg/ml and 120 µg/ml doses produced bacterial growth inhibition at par with standard antibiotic Vancomycin. This study highlights the efficacy of multi-herbal formulations in combating antibiotic resistant infections which can be utilized in clinical condition after thorough research and thus answers a solution for drug resistant infections.

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Please cite this article in press as **Shakkira. M. Haneefa et al.** Phytochemical Screening, HPTLC Profiling and Antibacterial Effect of Vilvadi tablet against *Staphylococcus aureus* and Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* – an in Vitro Study. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2022;12(10).

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INTRODUCTION

The emergence of multidrug-resistant pathogenic bacterial strains jeopardizes the worth of antibiotics, which have previously transformed the medical therapeutic paradigm [1]. Global surveillance report by WHO in 2014 states, antibiotic resistance is the most serious threat to global public health, food security, and development since the disconcerting reality of the loss of previously effective drugs, in combination with the slow discovery of new antibiotics, threatens, a post-antibiotic era of infectious incurable diseases [2]. A recent report estimates that 10 million deaths a year by 2050 due to antibiotic resistance unless a global strategy to address the problem is mounted [3]. WHO has recently enlisted ESKAPE pathogens (a group of six nosocomial pathogens: *Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus* (SA), *Klebsiellapneumoniae*, *Acinetobacterbaumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* & *Enterobacterspp*) in the global priority pathogen list against which new antibiotics are urgently needed[4]. *Staphylococcus* has a record of developing the resistance quickly and Methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) is categorized under the high priority group[4]. Recently, it has entered the spotlight as a globally pervasive drug-resistant pathogen and infections caused by it remain a significant cause of mortality and morbidity in tropical countries. Present guidelines revealed that many antibiotics suggested against ESKAPE have been deleted with the addition of relatively few antibiotics and antibiotic combinations. Furthermore, there are incidences of resistance against some of these newly added antibiotics. It is therefore imperative to find alternative ways to treat infections especially those caused by ESKAPE pathogens.

The alarming growth of MRSA and difficulties to treat the infections have initiated a search for new antibacterial compounds and to develop new alternative strategies in combating bacterial infections. Recent studies have proved the efficacy of plant-derived compounds with direct and indirect antibacterial activity in the form of antibiotic resistance modifying compounds in combination with antibiotics to increase their effectiveness[5]. This ability of plant active substances helps in modification or blocking of resistance mechanism so that bacterium becomes sensitive to antibiotic or even acts at a lower concentration.

Traditional systems of medicines like Ayurveda propagated several formulations for various ailments. As time advances, newer disease entities appear and the role of Ayurveda has been sidelined. With the advent of bacterial resistance and similar wide spread microbial infections have drawn attention to alternative measures to combat such diseases. Ayurvedic text promulgated a multi-drug formulation named Vilvadi tablet [6] as a remedy against infectious conditions. This study aimed at investigating on the efficacy of this formulation against *S.aureus* and MRSA infections as an in vitro study model.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Drug preparation:

The finely powdered crude drug of VT (Figure 1) were collected from Aryavaidyasala, Kottakkal and authenticated. All the ingredients were taken as per the proportion mentioned in Table 1 and were properly mixed together. The powder was then grinded by adding 9070 ml of freshly collected and pasteurized goat's urine, for a period of 120 hr. Finally, it was made into pills of uniform size, dried, stored and frozen till the study.

Table 1: Constituents of Vilvadi tablet.

Sl.no	Drug	Botanical name	Family	Common name	Parts used	Proportion
1	Vilva	<i>Aeglemarmelos</i> (L.) Corrêa	RutaceaeJuss	Bael tree Golden apple	Root bark	1 part
2	Surasaḥ	<i>Ocimumtenuiflorum</i> L	LamiaceaeMartinov	Holy basil	Inflorescence	1 part
3	Karañja	<i>Pongamiapinnata</i> (L.) Pierr	FabaceaeLindl	Indian beech	Seed	1 part
4	Nataṃ	<i>Valerianajatamansi</i> Jones ex Roxb.	ValerianaceaeBatsch	Indian valerian	Root	1 part
5	Surāhva	<i>Cedrusdeodara</i> (Roxb. ex D.Don) G.Don	Pinacea	Deodar	Heart wood	1 part
6	Harītakī	<i>Terminaliachebula</i> Retz.	Combretaceae R.Br	Chebulicmyrobalan	Fruit rind	1/3 part
7	Āmalakī	<i>Phyllanthusemblica</i> L.	PhyllanthaceaeMartinov	Emblicmyrobalan	Fruit rind	1/3 part
8	Vibhūtakī	<i>Terminaliabelirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.	Combretaceae R.Br	Bellericmyrobalan	Fruit rind	1/3 part
9	Pippalī	<i>Piper longum</i> L.	PiperaceaeGiseke	Indian long pepper	Dried spikes	1/3 part
10	Nāgaram	<i>Zingiberofficinale</i> Roscoe.	Zingiberaceae	Dry Ginger	Rhizome	1/3 part
11	Haricam	<i>Piper nigrum</i> L.	Piperaceae	Black pepper	Fruit	1/3 part
12	Haridrā	<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	ZingiberaceaeMartinov	Indian saffron	Rhizome	1/2 part
13	Dāruharidrā	<i>Berberisaristata</i> DC	BerberidaceaeJuss	Tree turmeric	Stem bark	1/2 part
14	Bastamūtra	<i>Capra aegAgrushircus</i>	Bovidae	-	Urine	9070 ml

Figure 1: Constituents of Vilvadi tablet.

Preparation of extracts:

VT samples were subjected to successive Soxhlet extraction using an eluotropic series of solvents (in the following order: cyclohexane (CH), ethyl acetate (EA), acetone (AC), methanol (MET) (70%)) by hot percolation method (Figure 2.D) [7]. The extracts were then concentrated at low temperature and pressure till the entire solvent was removed from the extracts (Figure 2.E). The prepared extracts were stored in labeled sterile screw capped bottles at -20°C and later used for further study.

Figure 2:A,B: stages during the preparation of medicine, C: prepared VT sample, D,E: stages during the extraction of VT sample.

Phytochemical screening:

Preliminary phytochemical screening of VT was done as per standard protocols [8, 9].

HPTLC Profile (High Performance Thin Layer Chromatography):

HPTLC study was done following the method of Harborne [8] and Ram et al [10]. An accurately weighed 1 gm of VT was extracted with HPTLC grade methanol & made up to 10 ml in a standard flask with methanol. A mobile phase of Toluene: Ethyl acetate: Formic acid: Methanol in the ratio of 7:5:1:0.5 was taken. 10 μ l of the test solution was spotted on the TLC Silica gel 60 F254 coated on Aluminium sheet of 10x10 cm using CAMAG Linomat V Automatic Sample Spotter and the chromatogram was developed using CAMAG twin trough glass chamber of 10 x 10 cm dimension. The developed plates were air dried and the documentation of the plate was carried out using CAMAG REPROSTAR 3 coupled with a CAMAG-TLC Scanner before and after derivatization in an iodine chamber at white light, UV 254 nm and UV 366 nm illumination mode. R_f values and fingerprint profiles were recorded using CAMAG HPTLC software.

Antibacterial study:

Bacterial strain:

The test organisms used for evaluation of antibacterial activity (ABA) included *Staphylococcus aureus* (SA), Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). Bacterial strain (*S. aureus* – MTCC 96) were purchased from MTCC, Chandigarh. While, MRSA were procured from locally collected clinical samples by repeated subculturing in salt stressed environment containing methicillin antibiotic [11] followed by confirmation with Cefoxitin disc diffusion test [12]. The bacterial strains were inoculated on Muller Hinton agar plates using sterile cell spreader in order to obtain uniform microbial growth and incubated at 37°C for 24 h and a single colony was obtained using a sterile loop and inoculated into Muller Hinton (MH) broth to form a homogenous suspension of the test organism.

Figure 3:E: Agar slant streaked with *S.aureus*.

F: Agar slant streaked with MRSA.

Extract dilution:

The crude extracts were dissolved separately and serially diluted in DMSO to make the extract into following 6 concentrations (480 μ g/ml, 240 μ g/ml, 120 μ g/ml, 60 μ g/ml, 30 μ g/ml and 15 μ g/ml).

Well diffusion method [13]:

Inocula were flooded onto the surface of Petri plates containing 25 ml of MH Agar. Wells of 3 mm diameter were cut in the agar using a sterile cork borer. Using a micropipette, aliquots (100 μ l) of the extracts were added into separate wells. After incubation overnight at 37 °C, the plates were examined and the diameter of the zone of inhibition was measured (Figure 4). The Vancomycin (30 μ g/ml) were used as positive control (Figure 4 D) while DMSO was used as the negative control (Figure 4: B, C). The plates were incubated for 24 h at 37°C. The antibacterial activity was evaluated by measuring diameter of inhibition zone. Experiment was carried out in triplicate and the averages diameter of zone of inhibition was recorded.

Figure 4: A: Cefoxitin disc diffusion test of MRSA, B: ABA of *S.aureus* in DMSO, C: ABA of MRSA in DMSO, D: ABA of *S.aureus* in Vancomycin, E: ABA of EA extract of VT on *S.aureus*, F: ABA of AC extract of VT on *S.aureus*, G: ABA of AC extract of VT on MRSA, H: ABA of EA extract of VT on MRSA.

Determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC):

The MIC of the extracts were determined by micro dilution technique [14] using 96 well microplate. All the wells of the microtiter plate were loaded with 100 μ L of fresh MH broth. To each 3 consecutive wells, 100 μ L of desired concentration of drug extract was added. 3 wells adjoining the respective doses were also loaded with drug extract; but no bacterial culture was added and served as the drug control. 3 consecutive wells were filled only with MH broth and served as the broth control. The optical density (OD) obtained in the drug control was subtracted from the OD of wells containing drugs along with the bacterial culture. Readings were taken at room temperature at 600 nm immediately after inoculating with bacterial culture. Readings were similarly taken after 24 h and 48 h of incubation and MIC was calculated using logistic regression curve.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The results of phytochemical screening are as shown in Table2.

Table 2: Preliminary screening of phytoconstituents in VT extracts.

Phytoconstituents& Tests		Cyclohexane	Ethyl acetate	Acetone	Methanol
alkaloids	Dragendorff's test	-	++	+	+++
	Hager's test	-	-	+	-
	Wagner's test	-	-	+++	++
	Mayer's test	+	-	+++	+++
	Froehde test	-	-	+	+
carbohydrates	Marquis test	-	-	+	+
	Molisch test	-	-	-	-
	Fehling test	+++	+++	+++	+++
Free aminoacids and protiens		-	-	-	-
Phenols	Ferric chloride test	-	+++	++	+++
Glycosides	Kellerkiliani test	+++	+++	+	+
Saponins	Froth test	-	-	-	+
	Foam test	-	-	-	+
Phytosterol	Salkowski test	+++	+++	-	+++
Fixed oils and fats		+++	+	+++	+
Resins		+++	++	-	+
Tannins	Ferric chloride	-	++	+++	++
Flavonoids	Alkaline reagent	+++	+	++	-
	Lead acetate	-	+++	+	+++

-absent, + mild, ++ moderate, +++ high presence.

The secondary metabolites produced by naturally occurring plant species are medically bioactive compounds that exert antimicrobial action through different mechanisms.

Alkaloids are potentially new type of natural antibiotic with a wide antibacterial spectrum, rare adverse reactions, and a low tendency to produce drug resistance [15]. The piperidine alkaloids present in the *Piper nigrum*, *Piper longum* have a promising bacteriostatic and bactericidal activities and can be used as a broad – spectrum antimicrobial agents [16]. It is a proved alkaloid against *S.aureus* with an inhibition zone of 18 mm and MIC: 50 mg/ml [17]. In addition to that, it has been found to enhance the therapeutic efficacy of many drugs by increasing oral bioavailability and by inhibiting various metabolizing enzymes [18]; and also has immune system enhancing property [19]. A proved example is the curcumin present in *Curcuma longa*, which cannot be utilized because of poor bioavailability due to its rapid metabolism in the liver and intestinal wall while its combination with piperine enhances its serum concentration and bioavailability [20]. Piperine also act as an inhibitor of Nor A efflux pumps which act as transport proteins involved in the release of toxic substrate from inside the cells to the external environment. These proteins are found in both Gram positive and negative bacteria [21]. Similarly, antibacterial properties have also been identified in quinoline alkaloids. An well-known example is Berberine alkaloid (isoquinoline alkaloid) present in *Berberis aristata* binds to FtsZ protein (assist cell division; act as homology to tubulin protein eukaryotes), causing the inhibition of FtsZ assembly and its GTPase activity, leading to cell elongation, which causes inhibition of cell division. Berberine alkaloid also exhibit antibacterial activity against *S.aureus* (MIC: 128 µg/mL) [20] as well as MRSA (MIC: 32 to 128 µg/mL) [22] by the inhibition of efflux pumps due to similarity with the substrate of the multi-drug resistance efflux pumps. Studies revealed that berberine along with antibiotics produced an additive effect which helps to arrest the growth of MRSA in an effective manner [23]. In addition to this, it can inhibit bacterial biofilm formation [24]. The other important alkaloid is Flavonoids which are known to be synthesized by plants in response to microbial infection; are proven to be effective antimicrobial substances against a wide array of microorganisms *in vitro* since they have the ability to complex with extracellular and soluble proteins present in the bacterial cell walls [25].

Phenolics are a class of plant secondary metabolites that contain one or more hydroxy derivatives of benzene rings that may exhibit significant antibacterial activity. Several studies suggest that, this activity may be by the modification in permeability of cell membranes, the changes in various intracellular functions induced by hydrogen binding of the phenolic compounds to enzymes or by the modification of the cell wall rigidity with integrity losses due to different interactions with the cell membrane [25].

Tannins are a diverse group of water-soluble plant secondary metabolite with high affinity for proteins. They has the ability to form complexes with antimicrobial peptide named proline rich protein; which eventually leads to the inhibition of cell wall synthesis in the bacteria [26].

The saponins cause the leakage of proteins and certain enzymes from the bacterial cell causing its disruption [27].

The Gallic acid present in the 3 constituents of Triphala (*Terminalia chebula* Retz, *Terminalia bellirica* (Gaertn.) Roxb, *Phyllanthus emblica* L.) proved to be an efficient antibacterial agent against *S.aureus* (MIC : 1750 mg/mL) due to its ability to cross over the cell membrane because of its partial lipophilic nature which in turn leads to localized hyperacidification of cytoplasm followed by protein denaturation and cell death [28].

All the extracts of VT samples are rich in secondary metabolites. These compounds may form a wide source of antibiotic resistance-modifying compounds and could increase the sensitivity of bacteria to antibiotics. However, activity does not depend only on the secondary metabolites in the plant extracts, but also on their concentration and the possible interaction with other components.

The results obtained from HPTLC fingerprint scanned at 254 nm wavelength, confirmed the presence of twelve different phytoconstituents with different R_f values. The corresponding R_f values recorded in the ascending order of 0.04 to 0.80, with maximum percentage of concentration 29.08 % at 0.71 R_f. At 366 nm, the chromatogram showed 9 peaks with R_f values in the ascending order of 0.04 to 0.70 with maximum percentage at 45.65% at 0.44 R_f. The chemical constituents with R_f values, maximum percentage, area percentage, present in the VT were tabulated in Table 3 and shown in Fig 5. Also, the spectra of the extract was depicted in Fig 5.

Table 3: R_f value and % area of VT at 254 nm & 366 nm.

AT 254 nm				AT 366 nm			
PEAK NO	R _f VALUE	AREA(AU)	% AREA(AU)	PEAK NO	R _f VALUE	AREA(AU)	% AREA(AU)
1	0.04	4281.1	10.86				
2	0.10	835.0	2.12				
3	0.13	1059.0	2.69	1	0.04	2826.0	5.77
4	0.19	158.2	0.40	2	0.10	2544.4	5.20
5	0.30	1472.1	3.74	3	0.28	830.2	1.70
6	0.35	5718.6	14.51	4	0.32	786.3	1.61
7	0.45	8828.4	22.40	5	0.36	1651.5	3.36
8	0.51	1233.1	3.13	6	0.44	22349.2	45.65
9	0.55	2411.0	6.12	7	0.52	314.2	0.64
10	0.61	515.0	1.31	8	0.58	2690.9	5.50
11	0.71	11460.0	29.08	9	0.70	14969.8	30.57
12	0.80	1433.1	3.64				
Total		39404.6		Total		48962.5	

Figure 5: HPTLC analysis of VT sample.

In the present study, the VT samples were tested for their antibacterial activity against *S.aureus* and MRSA in terms of reduction in zone of inhibition and was compared with the standard antibiotic Vancomycin. The details of zone of inhibition measured for various samples are presented in Table 4. Similarly the MIC was calculated and tabulated in Table 5. Results showed that VT possess pronounced antibacterial activity against MRSA in all the extracts in a dose dependent manner. Among all the extracts, EA extract (MIC: 123.91 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) at 480 μg (39.33 \pm 3.05 mm), 240 μg (36.33 \pm 1.15 mm), 120 μg (28.67 \pm 1.15 mm) and AC extract (MIC : 139.27 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) at 480 μg (33 \pm 1.73 mm), 240 μg (28 \pm 2 mm) possess strong antibacterial activity against MRSA which was found to be superior to that of standard (22.67 \pm 1.15 mm). On analyzing the antibacterial assay of VT on *S.aureus*, it was inferred that all the extracts except MET showed moderate antibacterial effect in a dose dependent manner while MET showed antibacterial effect only in the lower dose. Among all the extracts, AC (MIC: 138.1 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) and EA (MIC: 143.9 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) extracts at 480 μg (21.50 \pm 1.22 mm, 21.33 \pm 1.53mm respectively) exhibited antibacterial effect almost similar to that of standard (24.67 \pm 1.15 mm). The mean zone of inhibition of Dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) on MRSA and *S.aureus* were 3.00 \pm 0.00 mm, indicating that it doesn't have antibacterial effect. The plant extracts exerts the antibacterial effect through multitude of pathways. One important targets of plant extracts to produce the antibacterial effect is the inhibition of biofilm production. It could allow biofilm associated infections to be more effectively resolved[29]. Studies have shown that natural antimicrobial compounds such as herbal extracts affect bacterial antibiotic resistant biofilms like biofilm formed by MRSA[30]. Another mechanism of antimicrobial agents involves bacterial membrane permeabilization or disruption of membrane potential or inhibition of macromolecular synthesis. According to the present study, we can hypothesized that the hydrophobic nature of AC and EA extracts of VT may facilitate the permeation into bacterial cell membrane lipids and consequently increases its permeability and this function leads to impairment in all cellular activity related to cell membrane, departure of ions from the cell and finally cell death or it may have potential of inhibiting genes involved in biofilm formation in MRSA and more evaluation is required to conclusively state the mechanism of action of VT on both the bacterial strain.

Table 4: Mean zone of inhibition of different concentration of various extracts of VT, positive and negative control on bacterial strains.

Extracts of VA with concentration (µg/ml)	Mean zone of inhibition (mm)		
	SA	MRSA	
Cyclohexane	480	16.33±5.77 ^b	18.67±3.78 ^a
	240	12.00±1.00 ^b	13.00±1.00 ^b
	120	10.33±1.53 ^c	16.00±1.00 ^b
	60	9.67±1.55 ^c	11.67±0.58 ^b
	30	6.00±1.00 ^c	3.00±0.00 ^c
	15	3.00±0.00 ^c	3.00±0.00 ^c
Ethyl acetate	480	21.33±1.53 ^{ns}	39.33±3.05 ^{ns}
	240	19.67±2.08 ^{ns}	36.33±1.15 ^{ns}
	120	15.33±4.04 ^b	28.67±1.15 ^{ns}
	60	9.67±1.15 ^c	22.00±1.00 ^a
	30	10.00±1.73 ^c	18.00±1.00 ^b
	15	10.00±2.00 ^c	17.33±1.15 ^b
Acetone	480	21.50±1.22 ^{ns}	33±1.73 ^{ns}
	240	14.67±1.63 ^b	28±2.00 ^{ns}
	120	12.00±1.73 ^b	19.33±2.31 ^a
	60	10.00±1.00 ^c	16.33±0.58 ^a
	30	9.00±1.00 ^c	13.33±0.58 ^b
	15	8.00±1.00 ^c	8.67±1.15 ^c
Methanol	480	3.00±0.00 ^c	16±3.60 ^c
	240	3.00±0.00 ^c	13.33±1.53 ^b
	120	3.00±0.00 ^c	14.33±1.15 ^b
	60	8.67±1.53 ^c	15.67±1.15 ^b
	30	14.00±1.73 ^b	8.33±1.15 ^c
	15	10.67±0.58 ^c	9.67±2.31 ^c
DMSO (negative control)		3.00±0.01 ^c	3.00±0.01 ^c
Vancomycin (positive control)		24.67±1.15	22.67±1.15

('a'-significant at p<0.05, 'b' – significant at p<0.01, 'c'- significant at p <0.001, 'ns' – not significant (p>0.05))

Table 5: MIC of various extracts of VT on bacterial strains.

Extracts of VT	Minimum Inhibitory Concentration in µg/ml	
	SA	MRSA
Cyclohexane	187.6 µg/ml	211.91 µg/ml
Ethyl acetate	143.9 µg/ml	123.91 µg/ml
Acetone	138.1 µg/ml	139.27 µg/ml
Methanol	318.9 µg/ml	284.91 µg/ml
Vancomycin	0.25-1 □ g/ml[31]	0.125- 1 □□ g/ml[32]

CONCLUSION

The present research findings may provide an authentic conclusion that phytochemical screening of VT indicated the presence of many chemical constituents which are attributable for the varied pharmacological property including its antibacterial activity especially against the resistant strains. Although the exact active components of these extracts that showed antibacterial effect were not identified, yet the presence of antimicrobial active principles such as phenols, alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, and coumarins seems to cause these activities. It provides a lead for further investigation of its biological activity according to the presence of phytoconstituent groups.

The experimental results obtained from the present study illustrates that EA extract found to be more effective to control the growth of S.aureus while AC extract found to be more effective in MRSA. The activity of this herbal antitoxic formulation to inhibit the growth of bacteria even the antibiotic resistant strains is an indication of its broad spectrum antimicrobial activity, which may be employed as a source to develop new antimicrobial agents that can be used as a stand-alone treatment or as a conjoint therapy with other antibiotics. This experimental results provide an approach to exploit safe antibacterial agent against antibiotic resistant strains. To establish the mechanism of antibiotic resistance modifying effect of the drug, more evaluation by protein or gene expression is required.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are deeply indebted to the management of VPSV Ayurveda college, Kottakkal and Kerala University of health Sciences, Thrissur, Kerala.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None

ABBREVIATIONS:

SA	- <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
MRSA	- Methicillin Resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
VT	- Vilvadi tablet
MIC	- Minimum Inhibitory Concentration
DMSO	- Dimethyl Sulphoxide
OD	- Optical Density
MH	- Muller Hinton
ABA	- Antibacterial activity
AC	- Acetone
EA	- Ethyl acetate
CH	- Cyclohexane
MET	- Methanol

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